

Investigation of Factors Influencing Staff Motivation in Selected Secondary Schools of Isoka District in Zambia

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Abstract: The study focused on, 'Investigation of factors influencing staff motivation in selected secondary schools of Isoka District in Zambia. This study attempted to answer the following research questions (a). Are there some options in terms of factors that influence motivations among teachers? (b). What factors influence motivation of teachers in the secondary schools? The population of the study consisted of secondary school teachers and head teachers in the selected schools that were sampled in Isoka District. The instrument used for data collection were questionnaires that were prepared using open ended questions but were different for both head teachers and teachers. The major findings were that: (a) Improved living conditions of teachers especially in rural and remote areas influence motivation. (b) Improved condition of services for teachers influence motivation (c) Providing quality infrastructure, rewarding teachers in monetary terms, providing adequate teaching and learning material and better pay influence the motivation of teachers. (d) Allowing freedom of opinion among teachers is one of the factors that influence motivation. In this study the conclusions that came out of the findings as stated below. (a) Improved living conditions of teachers in rural and remote areas influenced motivations among teachers (b) Improved condition of service for teachers influence motivation among teachers (c) Providing quality infrastructure, rewarding teachers in monetary terms, providing adequate teaching and learning material and better pay influence motivation among teachers. (d) Allowing freedom of opinion among teachers is one of the factors that influence motivation among teachers. The recommendations of the study were (i) The government should help build housing units in rural and remote areas so as to improve the living conditions of teachers there by motivating them. (ii) The government should improve the conditions of service for teachers (iii) The headteachers should allow freedom of opinion among teachers

Keywords: Motivation; Influence; Teachers; Secondary school; Theories.

1. INTRODUCTION

Almost anyone can give an anecdotal example of a family member or friend who is smart, possibly even scores highly on tests, but never cared to engage in school and never got good grades. Why would such an intelligent child lack the drive to excel? Or what explanation is there for two siblings raised in the same household one of whom is extremely academically driven and the other of whom does not seem to care about academics at all? These are complex questions with no easy answers. But fundamentally, they point to one important issue, students' motivation to learn as provided for by the teacher.

A motive is a reason for doing something. Motivation is concerned with the strength and direction of behaviour and the factors that influence people to behave in certain ways. The term 'motivation' can refer variously to the goal's individuals have, the ways in which individuals chose their goals and the ways in which others try to change their behaviour. There are a number of motivation theories which, in the main, are complementary to one another. The most significant ones are those concerned with expectancy, goal setting and equity, which are classified as process or cognitive theories.

Instrumentality theory

This is a Taylorism type by the theorist Taylor put across in 1911. The theory summarizes that, if we do one thing it leads to another. People will be motivated to work if rewards and punishments are directly related to their performance. The implication of the theory is that Basis of crude attempts to motivate people by incentives. Often used as the implied rationale for performance-related pay although this is seldom an effective motivator.

Needs (content) theory

This is a Hierarchy of needs type by the theorist Maslow which he put across in 1954. The theory summarizes that a hierarchy of five needs exist: physiological, safety, social, esteem, self-fulfillment. Needs at a higher level only emerge when a lower need is satisfied. The theory Focuses attention on the various needs that motivate people and the notion that a satisfied need is no longer a motivator. The concept of a hierarchy has no practical significance.

Needs (content) theory

This is a Managerial needs theory by the theorist McClelland which he put across in 1973. The theory summarizes that Managers have three fundamental needs: achievement, affiliation and power. With implication that draws attention to the needs of managers and the important concept of 'achievement motivation'

The teacher is the one that translate educational objectives specified in the National Policy on Education, into knowledge and skill and transfer them to students in the classroom. Also, the government may establish new schools, effect changes in the structure of the curriculum, recommend and prescribe teaching methods, but in the end, the teacher will be responsible for applying them to attain the goal of teaching and learning. It is therefore very important the teacher who is at the center of this important task is motivated.

Teacher motivation has become an important issue given their responsibility to impart knowledge and skills to learners. It is argued that satisfied teachers are generally more productive and can influence students' achievement. However, measuring the determinants and consequences of work motivation is complex because these psychological processes are not directly observable and there are numerous organizational and environmental obstacles that can affect goal attainment (Mark,2015).

Teacher motivation depends critically on effective management, particularly at the school level. If systems and structures set up to manage and support teachers are dysfunctional, teachers are likely to lose their sense of professional responsibility and commitment. Teachers' management is most crucial at the school level, where the importance of teachers' work and their competence in performing it are crucially influenced by the quality of both internal and external supervision.

In a study by Vero and Puka (2017) on the importance of motivation in an education environment, they reported that, in the motivational aspect, the role of teachers in the educational process is the creation of a climate and a positive attitude that encourages learning and their long-term success. While the role of students is qualitative knowledge processing and being active in order to increase their academic. Increasing collaborative and communicative force between student and instructor are two basic factors of motivation for learning.

A study by Ikurite and Meindinyo (2017) which indicate that the factors that are currently being used to motivate teachers namely; annual get together parties, organizing send-off parties for teachers on transfer, constant supervision of teacher's work, provision of attendance register and provision of movement books have minimal influence on teachers performance while that factor such as age, subprofessional training may affect a teacher's performance. Based on these findings it was recommend that; management of secondary schools should make use of correct motivational strategies such as attitude

motivation, incentives, and recognition. there should be regular training for teachers' workshops to motivate teacher for higher productivity. Government should always try as much as possible to pay teachers' salaries promptly and regularly.

A study by Mupwaya et al (2021) on the factors that influence teachers' job satisfaction and motivation in public secondary schools in Chibombo district, Zambia showed high levels of satisfaction with their abilities. The study further reveals a number of factors that have been found to contribute to teacher job satisfaction amongst the secondary schools and these are salary, promotion opportunities, job grading systems and professional development activities. In terms of motivation it was found out that salary, relationship with students, administrative factors, nature of work, recognition and rewards systems, promotion opportunities and relationship with colleagues are the major factors contributing to staff motivation.

Muriithi (2020) conducted a study on motivation in which the study noted that most teachers were not offered salaries that were commensurate with the amount and quality of work, many head teachers are not supportive, and teachers generally feel unsupported and unappreciated by the school management. The study recommended that the private primary schools should strive to improve compensations, provide a more conducive working environment, promote team work among teachers, ensure teachers have a reasonable workload and have job security.

Statement of the problem

This study focused upon investigation of factors influencing staff motivation in selected secondary schools of Isoka district in Zambia

Research questions

This study attempted to answer the following research questions

- a. Are there some options in terms of factors that influence motivations among teachers?
- b. What factors influence motivation of teachers in the secondary schools?

2. METHODOLOGY

The study design that was used to carry out this was the survey study design that was conducted among selected secondary schools in Isoka District of Muchinga Province in Zambia.

Population of the study

The population of the study consisted of secondary school teachers and Headteachers in the selected schools that were sampled in Isoka District.

Sample Size

The minimum sample size was obtained using Cochran's Formula in its modification state.

$n = \frac{N}{1 + (280/1000)}$ where n = sample size, N =population size.

$n = 218.7$

Thus, the sample size for this study was 219.

Research instruments.

The instruments which were used questionnaires were prepared using open ended questions but were different for both Headteachers and teachers.

Data analysis

The data obtained were checked for completeness and for any errors that could have occurred. The responses on the questionnaires were arranged in themes and later common and emerging themes were obtained. Microsoft word was used to produce tables in reader format. From this the conclusion emerged out and recommendations were recorded.

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Analysis of parameters
Table 1: Opinion on Some factors that influence motivation as given by teachers.

Respondents	Motivation strategies
Respondent 177	Improve living conditions of teachers especially in rural and remote areas.
Respondents 199	Teacher motivation, allowing freedom of opinion
Respondent 1	Improve the condition of services for teachers
Respondent 8	Maintain infrastructure, quality of teaching and teachers

Source: Field Data, 2022

The above table gives out responses as they emerged in themes and this shows the common motivation strategies as options given out by teachers.

Table 2: Some factors that influence motivation as given by Head teachers.

Motivation teachers like	Response
Respondent 5	Money
Respondent 7	Improving conditions of service in form of emoluments
Respondent 4	Both extrinsic through improved condition of service and intrinsic through promotions and recognition of one's achievements
Respondent 1	Provide quality infrastructure, reward teachers in monetary terms, provide adequate teaching/learning material and better pay

Source: Field Data, 2022

The above table gives out responses as they emerged in themes and this shows the common factors that influence motivation as given out by Headteachers.

3. FINDINGS

The major findings were that:

- a. Improved living conditions of teachers especially in rural and remote areas influence motivation.
- b. Improved condition of services for teachers influence motivation
- c. Providing quality infrastructure, reward teachers in monetary terms, providing adequate teaching and learning material and better pay influence the motivation of teachers.
- d. Allowing freedom of opinion among teachers is one of the factors that influence motivation.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study the conclusions came out of the findings were as stated below.

- a. Improved living conditions of teachers in rural and remote areas influenced motivations among teachers
- b. Improved condition of service for teachers influenced motivation among teachers
- c. Providing quality infrastructure, reward teachers in monetary terms, providing adequate teaching and learning material and better pay influenced motivation among teachers.
- d. Allowing freedom of opinion among teachers is one of the factors that influenced motivation among teachers

5. RECOMENDATIONS

Findings were attained from the data analysis and conclusions that came into view gave rise to some recommendations as given below.

- i. The government should help build housing units in rural and remote areas so as to improve the living conditions of teachers there by motivating them.
- ii. The government should improve the conditions of service for teachers
- iii. The Headteachers should allow freedom of opinion among teachers.

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